

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B098
Date: 26 May 2005
Take Off 09:44:18
Landing: 13:29:58
Flight Time 3h 45m 40

Campaign: CWVS / CIRRUS
Trials Instructions:
Operating Area: Chilbolton

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Charlie Whitaker	BAES
3	CCM	Sue Angold	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Richard Cotton	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM
6	CCN/CVI	Paul James	FAAM
7	Core Chemistry	Alan Woolley	FAAM
8	Cloud Physics	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
9	CPI	Keith Bower	Manchester
10	AMS	Jonny Crosier	Manchester
11	Observer	Steve Ball	FAAM
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Flight Track:

B098 Track 26-MAY-05

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B098
 Date: 26 May 2005
 Project: CWVS / Cirrus
 Location: Chilbolton

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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092851		INU to NAV Cranfield	0.30 kft	125 52	04.36N 000 37.48W
094418		T/O Cranfield	2.4 kft	316	09:44:18
094932		ASPs open	5.0 kft	263	
095328		video tapes	5.0 kft	225	FFC & DFC to record
100759	102232	Profile 1	3.6 - 18.0 kft	256	3500' to fl240 interrupted at fl180
102721	103514	Profile 1.2	18.0 - 25.0 kft	083	recommended interrupted at fl250
104107	104538	Profile 1.3	25.0 - 28.0 kft	250	recommended to fl280
105255	105943	Run 1	22.1 - 22.0 kft	086	fl220
110237	110832	Run 2	21.0 - 21.1 kft	251	fl210
111258	111853	Run 2.2	21.0 kft	087	towards Chilbolton overhead
112620	113258	Run 3	23.0 kft	252	fl230
113650	114055	Run 4	25.0 kft	079	fl250
114355	114906	Run 4.2	25.1 - 25.0 kft	255	fl 250 outbound
114921		Nev calcs	25.0 kft	258	
115345	115717	Run 5	27.0 kft	071	fl270
120028	121207	Run 5.2	27.1 - 27.0 kft	255	
121529	122232	Profile 2	27.1 - 32.0 kft	075	
122626	122908	Profile 2.2	32.1 - 33.1 kft	245	
123909	124520	Run 6	20.1 - 20.0 kft	088	fl200
125034	125607	Run 7	16.1 kft	250	fl160
130001	130406	Run 7.2	16.1 kft	080	
130450		end of science	15.0 kft	076	
130754		asp closed	7.0 kft	357	
132958		land Cranfield	0.28 kft	355	13:29:58
133448		Cranfield apron2	0.28 kft	307 52	04.36N 000 37.48W

B098 Track 26-MAY-05

4°W 3°W 2°W 1°W 0°

Mission Scientist's Log

M. Sci - Richard Cotton.

CWVC 2.2

Flight No **B.096**.....

Date 26/05/05.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
	T to Chl	5000'	163	51.7N/1.6W	CPI / ADA not seeing anything
10:07:36	P1 st	3500'			Initial Profile 3500-24000
10:18:50		14200			-4.79 / -10.25°C 590mb
10:21:40		17000			-11.4 / -14.71 25ms/22
10:22:31	P2 mt	FL180	248		
	P1 rec	FL180			-13.3 / -16.29 28ms/226
					Radar seeing cloud 20000-36000'
10:28:08					Inbound 100km Range
					CPI seeing crystals -
10:33:36	P1 st	23600	77	51.0/1.6W	-22.8 / -24.96°C 23/235° 393
10:35:13	P1 mt	25000			Combinations: Pdots, Binned R., poly X, S10, Drops?
10:38:00	P1 mt.	25000	251	51.0/1.6W	-26.05 / -27.24 375mb 26/233°
10:41:07	P1 rec.	FL250	251		→ FL280
10:41:08					
10:45:38	P1.3rd	FL280			End profile
10:46:40					Run 3 ADA (forget to start it) - sunlight only laser ~ 310
10:47:00					PCASP low 30/cm ³ measured Rad 0.2
10:48:19					AMS Wulms - turning TOF off CPC ~ 300
					ADA - No signal on Shilled - 120 on VSh
10:52:56	R1 st	FL220	79	50.9/2.6W	-19.4 / -19.11°C 20ms/231° 427mb
					80m
					vSIR + feathers Poly Xinds - 2D too
10:59:43	R1 end	FL22			End m
					Radar has Problem - can't see out for - go out to 60k

Mission Scientist's Log

M Sci - Richard Cotton.

CWVC 2.2

Flight No **B.098**.....

Date **26/05/05**.....

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	GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
Out	11:02:36	R2 _{st}	FL 210	250	51.0N/1.6W	24/234° -16.85 / 17.53°C 44Smb (226 465)
	11:06:52	R2 _{end}	FL 210	"	50.9/2.2W	-17.58/-17.08 44Smb 10mb/233° (^{block} 194 / ^{unch} 276 ^{block} 230 / ^{ch} 230 - No Skiller)
in.	11:12:58	R2.1 _s	FL 210	80	51.0/2.1W	To go ahead ChB. -17.69/-17.04 21/239 465
	11:18:55	R2.1 _e	FL 210	"	51.1/1.4W	Overhead ChB - end -16.50/-17.79 28/246 CEN Spectra Completed.
Out	11:26:19	R3	FL 230	252	51.0/1.6W	-21.66/-20.5°C 23/233 400mb CPI
	11:30:38					Come out of dead layer
	11:32:58	R3 _{end}	FL 230			End of Run - do re-orientation at FL 250
in.	11:36:49	R4 _{st}	FL 250	79	50.9/2.3W	-25.9/-24.98 375mb 21/244° 344mb
	11:40:58	R4 _{end}	FL 250		51.0/1.6W	
Out	11:43:54	R4.2 _{st}	FL 250	255	51.0/1.6W	375 -25.9/-24.83 25/235
	11:48:59	R4.2 _{end}	FL 250		50.9/2.2W	-27.5/-25.5°C 33/235
in.	11:53:46	R5	FL 270	72	50.9/2.2W	-30.77/-28.83 26/245 344mb (324mb)
	11:57:18	R5 _{end}			51.0/1.7W	343mb etc
Out	12:00:27	R5.2 _{st}	FL 270		51.0/1.6W	343 28/233 -30.87/-29.55°C
	12:12:08	R5.2 _{end}	FL 270	269	50.5/2.9W	344. -30.42/-29.03°C 24/249.
in.	12:15:29	P2	FL 270		50.5/2.8W	P2. start - towards ChB - Clear Air Cloud to South - can't go there
	12:22:32	P2.1	FL 320		51.0/1.6W	end Probe - Diving
Out	12:26:26	P2.2 _{st}	FL 320	246	51.0/1.7	-43.6/-42.55 32/241 272mb
Out	12:29:08	P2.2 _{end}	FL 330			end - descending to bottom C _i Descent to ground for C _{pi} - Error Will Stop / Start Probe

CORE CHEMISTRY PRE FLIGHT LOG

PRE POWER UP	
All sample lines are connected to the rack	Y
All cylinders pressures are OK	Y
Ozone Span = 504, Offset = 50	Y

GAS PRESSURES	N ₂ (bar)	CO ₂ / Argon (bar)	CO standard (bar)
PRE FLIGHT	52	128	135
POST FLIGHT	30	125	135

POST POWER UP – GROUND				
Ozone Sample Flow 1 (LPM)	Ozone Sample Flow 2 (LPM)	NO _x Sample Flow (LPM)	NO _x Ozonator Flow (LPM)	SO ₂ Sample Flow (LPM)
.4	.4	1.108	.065	.437
CO Time check against HORACE	CO Lamp Flow (ml/min)	Pressure Monochromator (bar)	Pressure Cell (Torr)	
Spot on!	33.95	1.09	7.13	

ZEROS							Average
Ozone (ppbV)	-1	1	0	-2	-2	-1	-0.8
NO (ppbV)	13.8	13.7	13.8	13.8	13.8	13.7	13.8
NO₂ (ppbV)	14.0	14.0	13.6	13.2	12.9	12.7	13.4
NO_x (ppbV)	27.7	27.4	27.4	26.7	26.7	26.4	27.1
SO₂ (ppbV)	-.71	-.21	-.42	-.54	-.09	-.52	-.42

PRE FLIGHT COMMENTS

Apparent NO_x leak. Zeros rubbish and leak test flow does not approach zero.

CORE CHEMISTRY CALIBRATION AND FLOW LOG

PREVIOUS CO CAL		Date and Flight Level	Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)
10:00 ish Bad cal	50	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		19.67	335.95	6608.59	50	7.13	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO ₂ Sample
		33.87	.5	.5	1.100	.0063	.4
10:11:08 Bad cal	35	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		75.05	85.45	6638.57	50	7.13	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO ₂ Sample
		33.88	0.6	0.7	1.101	0.067	.366
11:03:48	220	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		80.43	81.27	6536.16	50	7.14	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO ₂ Sample
		33.48	.8	.8	1.023	.066	.220
11:17:24	210	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		81.81	80.26	6565.67	50	7.13	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO ₂ Sample
		33.93	.8	.8	1.022	0.066	0.216
11:29:43	230	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		82.16	80.15	6584.82	50	7.14	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO ₂ Sample
		33.89	0.8	0.8	0.067	1.017	0.198
11:40:02	250	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		82.09	79.50	6526.3	50	7.14	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO ₂ Sample
		33.93	.8	.8	1.002	.068	.170
11:55:46	270	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		81.46	80.01	6517.8	50	7	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO ₂ Sample
		33.94	.8	.8	1.012	.066	.151

Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
12:25:48	320	78.61	82.11	6454.25	50	6.27	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.82	.8	.8	.947	.062	0
Time	Flight Level	CO					
12:37:40	200	Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		79.87	80.67	6443.63	50	7.13	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.82	0.8	.8	1.019	0.066	.231
Time	Flight Level	CO					
12:53:36	160	Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		80.55	81.02	6526.37	50	7.13	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.88	.8	.8	1.051	.066	.278
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample

FLIGHT NUMBER: B098	DATE: 26/05/05	OPERATOR: Alan Woolley	Page 4 of 4
PROJECT: CWVC, then CIRRUS when Chilbolton Radar broke...			

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG

GENERAL COMMENTS

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B098

Date: 26/05/05

Operator: JT

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
10:07:58	0	0	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Profile 1 @ 3500ft
10:08:37	0	0	10	1000	0	0	0	0	0	0	4000ft
10:09:33	14	0.07	11	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	5000ft
10:10:34	12	0.07	11	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	6
10:11:31	2	0.07	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7
10:12:24	32	0.08	11	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	8
10:13:27	27	0.08	11	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	9
10:14:29	28	0.08	11	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	10
10:15:27	37	0.08	11	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	11
10:16:29	20	0.08	11	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	12
10:17:24	15	0.08	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	13
10:18:30	13	0.09	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14
10:19:27	28	0.09	11	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	15
10:20:27	17	0.09	11	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	16
10:21:27	21	0.09	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	17
10:22:30	16	0.09	11	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	18 profile interputed
10:27:21	30	0.09	12	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	18 profile restarted
10:28:33	13	0.08	12	70	1	400	10	83	400	10	19
10:29:30	8	0.19	12	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	20
10:30:42	3	0.1	12	0	14	625	10	700	200	10	21
10:31:49	0	0.05	12	10	0.5	100	10	100	200	10	22
10:32:56	0	0.08	12	5	4.5	100	8	2800	200	8	23
10:34:08	0	0	12	0	3.5	200	8	33	200	8	24
10:35:13	2	0.1	13	100	15	450	8	3733	200	8	25 profile interrupted temp -26 dp
10:41:27	11	0.18	21	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	25 profile restarted
10:42:33	7	0.15	21	10	6	475	8	Noise			26
10:44:18	7	0.7	22	2	0	0	0	Noise	0	0	27
10:45:35	2	1.1 ??	23	100	11	250	10	Noise			28 profile stop
10:52:56	2	0.5	27	75	15	400	8	1725	400	8	Run 1 @ FL220
10:54:00	1	0.06	27	0	0.5	200	10	83	200	10	
10:56:00	6	0.1	27	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
10:58:10	7	0.7	27	80	25	525	8	2700	200	8	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B098

Date: 26/05/05

Operator: JT

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
10:59:45	8	0.06	28	10	17	500	9	1000	500	9	End or run 1
11:02:36	15	0.07	29	2	0	0	0	2000	200	8	Start run 2 @ FL210
11:04:00	21	0.15	29	10	6	650	8	975	800	8	
11:06:00	13	0.1	30	2	2	800	8	333	800	8	
11:08:30	7	0.14	30	70	4	500	8	1933	100	8	End of run 2
11:12:58	11	0.45	35	100	30	700	8	2983	100	8	Start run 2.1
11:14:00	20	0.15	35	10	3	600	8	283	1000	8	
11:16:00	19	0.07	36	10	7	600	8	3250	1500	8	
11:18:53	36	0.6	38	100	53	525	8	2883	800	8	End of run 2.1
11:26:20	1	0.1	42	100	44	375	8	4458	100	8	Start run 3 FL230
11:28:00	16	0.7	44	200	50	700	8	10650	800	8	
11:30:00	205	1.1	47	60	0.5	200	8	2750	500	8	
11:32:32	12	0.06	47	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	End of run 3
11:36:50	9	0.31	47	10	0.5	375	8	150	400	8	Start run 4 @ FL250
11:38:00	4	0.07	47	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
11:40:55	82	1.06	48	100	36	625	8	10983	800	8	End of Run 4
11:43:55	24	0.8	55	100	46	800	8	12691	800	8	Start of run 4.1
11:45:00	37	0.85	58	150	22	600	9	1150	600	9	
11:47:00	250	0.93	59	100	150	425	8	900	400	8	
11:49:46	7	0.29	60	100	18	200	10	700	400	10	End of run 4.1
11:53:45	2	0.05	60	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start Run 5 @ FL270
11:55:00	1	0.05	60	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
11:57:16	4	0.05	60	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	End of Run 5
12:00:27	1	0	61	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start of Run 5.1
12:02:00	1	0.05	61	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
12:04:00	1	0.06	61	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
12:06:00	12	0.16	61	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
12:08:00	16	0.07	61	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
12:10:00	4	0.08	61	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
12:12:07	11	0.1	61	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	End Run 5.1
12:15:29	10	0.07	61	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start Profile @ FL270
12:16:42	3	0.07	61	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL280

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B

Date:

Operator:

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
12:17:51	4	0.08	61	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL290
12:19:00	2	0.08	61	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL300
12:20:29	2	0.08	61	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL310
12:22:32	5	0.06	61	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL320 End of Profile 2.1
12:26:26	1	0.11	61	0	0	0	0	37345 NOISE			FL320 recommence profile
12:29:08	4	0.09	61	2	0	0	0	NOISE			FL330 end of profile
12:39:09	7	0.08	61	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start run 6 @ FL200
12:41:00	7	0.07	61	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
12:43:00	14	0.07	61	0	0.5	100	1? sph	0	0	0	(spherical but -17C)
12:45:20	14	0.08	62	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	N.B. FFSSP 20 sec late
											End of run
											N.B. FFSSP 20 sec late
12:50:34	19	0.1	62	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start run 7 @ FL160
12:52:00	4	0.09	62	10	2.5	800	9	108	1000	9	
12:54:00	45	0.1	62	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
12:56:00	26	0.09	62	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	End of run 7
13:00:01	41	0.09	62	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start of run 7.1
13:02:00	42	0.08	62	7	1.5	800	8	280	800	8	
13:04:00	98	0.14	62	0	5	800	8	183	1000	8	End run 7

Flight No B098

CCNC LOG

Exp. Chilbortha.

Date 26/5/05

PAPS.

Page 1 of

ALLEVIATOR GMT		Height	TEMP INLET	STATIC						REMARKS
ON	OFF			1	2	3	4	5		
111320	111400	210	25	0.49	0.72	1.08	1.41	2.05	S	
			24.49	486	651	875	642	754	D	
			24.49	389	388	385	386	393	B	
			26.07	2278	2287	2295	2300	2307	R	
				896.4	896.1	895.7	896.1	896.1	P	
<u>Run</u>			27.05	0.5	0.74	1.1	1.41	2.07	S	
4	113733	250	24.14	477	463	603	1227	1400	D	
	113815		22.7	417	412	410	424	463	B	
			22.64	2311	2324	2328	2327	2329	R	
			23.09	856	857	857	856	856.3	P	
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5		
1153	115345	270	23	0.50	0.72	1.1			S	
			23	349	409				D	<u>Failed</u>
				409	410	410			B	
				2304	2305	2300			R	
				836.8	836	837.7			P	
			22.65	0.5	0.73	1.09	1.42	2.07	S	
120110	1202	270	23.06	431	443	440	428	450	D	
				393	406	412	413	413	B	
				2286	2286	2285	2279	2279	R	
				836.4	836.8	836	837	837	P	
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5		
123930	124016	160	24	0.51	0.71	1.08	1.4	2.02	S	
			23.71	431	444	589	820	623	D	
			23.5	399	416	426	430	438	B	
			24.5	424	2279	2294	2296	2288	R	
			24.5	904	922	937	937.6	937	P	
125515	1256	160	24.75	0.5	0.72	1.1			S	
			24	484	497	648			D	
			24	412	454	468			B	
					2349	2356			R	
				2278	937.4	937.6			P	
				937.3						

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B098**

Date: 25/05/05

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		Y	<u>Probes</u>		
GPS		Y	FFSSP	Y	Y
Satcom C		Y	PCASP	Y	Y
Satcom H		Y	2D-P	Y	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>			2D-C	Y	Y
De-Iced Temp		Y	Cloudscope	N	N
Non De-Iced		Y	SID 1	Y	Y
Heimann	N		SID 2	Y	N
<u>Hygrometers</u>					
G. Eastern		Y	HVPS	N	
J. Williams		Y	CIP25	Y	N
Nevzorov		Y	CIP100	Y	N
TWC		Y			
FWVS	Y	N	<u>Racks:</u>		
<u>Radiometers</u>			INC	Y	N
Upper Clear	Y	Y	CCN / CNC	Y	Y
“ Red	Y	Y	CVI	Y	Y
“ Silicon	Y	Y			
“ JO1D	N		<u>Aerosol</u>		
Lower Clear	Y	Y	PSAP	Y	N
“ Red	Y	Y	Nephelometer	N	
“ Silicon	Y	Y	Filters	Y	n
“ JO1D	N		AMS	Y	y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	N				
MARSS	N				
DEIMOS	N		<u>Others:</u>		
ARIES	N		NIR TDLAS	Y	N
SWS	N		2BT O3	Y	N
<u>Chemistry</u>			VACC	Y	N
Ozone	Y	Y	PEROXIDE	Y	N
ECGC	N		Formaldehyde	Y	N
NOX	Y	Y	ADA	Y	n
CO	Y	Y	CPI	Y	Y
ORAC	Y	N	NOxy	Y	n
PAN	Y	N	PTRMS		n
PERCA	Y	N	Bag Sampling		n
WAS	Y	n			

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B098

Date: 26/05/05

Instruments

1. Video – RFC display out of focus. Inboard display switches off .
2. otherwise ops normal:
 3. Cloud Physics
 4. core chem
 5. CCN

Aircraft

Nil